

LARGE SETS OF t -DESIGNS AND A RAMSEY-TYPE PROBLEM

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Abstract

For a given r -uniform hypergraph H and for given integers $p > q > 0$, $R_q^p(H; r)$ is the smallest positive integer m such that in every p -coloring of the edges of the complete r -uniform hypergraph K_m^r there is a copy of H with edges colored by at most q colors. Here we extend some previous results when $H = K_{r+1}^r$.

Budden, Stender and Zhang recently [1] considered the following hypergraph version of a graph Ramsey-type number initiated in [3, 4]. For a given r -uniform hypergraph H and for given integers $p > q > 0$, $R_q^p(H; r)$ is the smallest positive integer m such that in every p -coloring of the edges of the complete r -uniform hypergraph K_m^r there is a copy of H with edges colored by at most q colors. For $q = 1$ this definition gives the traditional p -color Ramsey number of H .

It was proved in [1] that $7 \leq R_2^3(K_4^3; 3) \leq 8$. The upper bound was derived from the result that the K_4^3 versus $K_4^3 - e$ Ramsey number ($K_4^3 - e$ is the hypergraph with three triples on four vertices) is 8 [8]. In fact, one can derive more from a Turán number. Turán's famous problem [9] is to determine $T(n)$, the smallest positive integer ℓ with the following property: there exist ℓ triples in an n -element set S such that every 4-subset of S contains at least one of the ℓ triples. For the state of the art on $T(n)$, see [7].

Proposition 1. *We have $R_2^3(K_4^3; 3) = 7$.*

Proof. The lower bound is the 3-coloring of K_6^3 given in [1]. On the other hand, in every 3-coloring of $K = K_7^3$ there is a color class, say red, with at most 11 triples. Because $T(7) = 12$ is known from [6], there must be a $K_4^3 \subset K$ containing no red triples. \square

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In the rest of this note we consider the case $H = K_{r+1}^r, p = r + 1, q = r$. Set $f(r) = R_r^{r+1}(K_{r+1}^r; r)$, i.e. $f(r)$ is the smallest integer m such that in every $(r + 1)$ -coloring of the edges of K_m^r there is a copy of K_{r+1}^r with its edges colored by at most r colors. It is known that $f(2) = 5$ ([4]), $f(3) = 5$ ([1]). Since among the $r + 2$ edges containing a fixed set of $r - 1$ vertices in an $(r + 1)$ -colored K_{2r+1}^r there are two edges with the same color, one gets the following upper bound.

Proposition 2. ([1]) For all $r \geq 1, f(r) \leq 2r + 1$.

Here we give a formula for $f(r)$ that connects it to the existence problem of large sets of t -designs and provides $f(r)$ for infinitely many r .

For $1 \leq t < k < v$, a $t - (v, k)$ design is a set of k -subsets of a v -set that covers each t -subset of the v -set exactly once. A large set of $t - (v, k)$ designs is a partition of the set of all k -subsets of a v -set into $t - (v, k)$ designs. The size N of a large set is the number of $t - (v, k)$ designs in the partition,

$$N = \frac{\binom{v}{k} \binom{k}{t}}{\binom{v}{t}}.$$

Here we defined only a special case of designs needed for our purposes; for more details see Chapter 4.4 of [5].

Let $g(r)$ be the smallest v in the form $v = r + t + 1$ for which there is no large set of $t - (v, t + 1)$ designs. Note that these large sets (if they exist) must have size $r + 1$, since

$$(r + 1) = \frac{\binom{r+t+1}{t+1} \binom{t+1}{t}}{\binom{r+t+1}{t}}.$$

Theorem 1. For all $r \geq 1, f(r) = g(r)$.

Proof. Suppose that $v = g(r) = r + t + 1$ and we have an $(r + 1)$ -coloring c on the edges of K_v^r . Let K be the vertex set of K_v^r . We claim that some $K_{r+1}^r \subset K_v^r$ is colored with at most r colors. Indeed, otherwise every $(r + 1)$ -element subset S of K would receive all of the $r + 1$ colors on their r -element subsets. The coloring c naturally defines a coloring c^* on the complements of the edges of K_v^r by defining $c^*(K \setminus e) = c(e)$ for all $e \in E(K_v^r)$. Since $|K| - |e| = v - r = t + 1$, c^* colors the $(t + 1)$ -element subsets of K . Moreover, for any t -element subset $T \subset K$ and for any color, say red, there is a unique red edge $e \subset K \setminus T$ in coloring c , thus the complement of e is the unique red $(t + 1)$ -element set in the coloring c^* that covers T . Thus each color class of c^* is a $t - (v, t + 1)$ design and the color classes define a large set of designs (of size $r + 1$), contradicting to the definition of $g(r)$. \square

Corollary 1. We have $f(4) = 7$.

Proof. There is a large set of $1 - (6, 2)$ designs: the factorization of K_6 . However, as known from Cayley [2], there is no large set of $2 - (7, 3)$ designs. \square

Corollary 2. For all $r \geq 1$, $f(r) = r + 2$ if r is odd and $f(r) = r + 3$ if $r \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$.

Proof. If r is odd, there is no $1 - (r + 2, 2)$ design, let alone a large set of them. If $r \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$ then there are large sets of $1 - (r + 2, 2)$ designs: the factorizations of K_{r+2} . However, no $2 - (r + 3, 3)$ design exists, since it would be a Steiner triple system on $r + 3$ points implying $r + 3 \equiv 1$ or $3 \pmod{6}$. However, in our case $r + 3 \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. \square

Corollary 3. We have $f(6) > 9$.

Proof. Large sets of $1 - (8, 2), 2 - (9, 3)$ designs exist. See [5], Large sets of t -designs, Chapter 4.4. \square

Remark. To determine $f(6)$ one has to decide whether there are large sets (of size 7) for the $3 - (10, 4), 4 - (11, 5), 5 - (12, 6)$ designs. If the last one exists then the upper bound $f(6) \leq 13$ in Proposition 2 would be sharp.

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References

- [1] M. Budden, M. Stender and Y. Zhang, Weakened Ramsey numbers and their hypergraph analogues, *Integers* **17** (2017), 1-8.
- [2] A. Cayley, On triadic arrangements of seven and fifteen things, *London, Edinburgh and Dublin Philos. Mag. Sci.* **37** (1850), 50-53.
- [3] K. Chung, M. Chung and C. Liu, A generalization of Ramsey theory for graphs - with stars and complete graphs as forbidden subgraphs, *Congressus Numerantium* **19** (1977), 155-161.
- [4] K. Chung and C. Liu, A generalization of Ramsey theory for graphs, *Discrete Mathematics* **21** (1978), 117-127.
- [5] C. J. Colbourn, J. H. Dinitz editors, *Handbook of Combinatorial Designs*, CRC Press, 2006.
- [6] Gy. Katona, T. Nemetz and M. Simonovits, On a problem of Turán in the theory of graphs, (in Hungarian, English summary), *Matematikai Lapok* **15** (1964), 228-238.
- [7] P. Keevash, Hypergraph Turán problems, *Surveys in Combinatorics, London Math. Soc. Lecture Note Ser. 392*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2011.
- [8] S. Radziszowski, Small Ramsey numbers, revision 15, *Electronic J. of Combinatorics* **DS 1.15** (2017), 1-104.
- [9] P. Turán, Research problem, *Közl. MTA Mat. Kutató Int.* **6** (1961), 177-181.